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Re-examining the Role of Global Textbooks in Higher Education: A Case Study from Vietnam

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Abstract

This article is based on a study that investigated the pedagogical impact of global English textbooks on teaching and learning processes in higher education, with a specific focus on Vietnamese universities. Through a mixed-methods case study design, the research explored how international textbooks are used by lecturers and perceived by students, examining their role in shaping classroom practices and learning outcomes. Findings from interviews with lecturers of English and survey data from students indicate that while textbooks provide structured content, pedagogical support, and assessment alignment, their effectiveness is moderated by factors such as cultural relevance, student proficiency, and teacher adaptability. The study highlights the need for critical engagement with textbook materials. This study also found that the lecturers involved demonstrated consistently high levels of creativity and autonomy when working with global English textbooks. These insights are valuable for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers navigating textbook-driven instruction in diverse higher education contexts. Although focused on a single case, research in Vietnam has significance due to its position as one of the world's fastest-developing economies. It may also have potential relevance for our understanding of textbook use globally, within other rapidly developing countries, in which the learning of English is a focus of recent government policy.

Keywords: Global English textbooks, TESOL, Vietnamese Universities, teacher autonomy

1 Introduction

In recent decades, the use of global textbooks in English language teaching (ELT) has become widespread, particularly in non-English-speaking countries where English is taught as a second or foreign language. These textbooks, often developed and published by Western publishers, are considered by many institutions to be a standard resource for instruction. Yet, their implementation raises important questions about pedagogical fit, cultural relevance, and learning effectiveness.

Vietnam provides a compelling case for examining the impact of global textbooks in higher education. As part of the country's ambitious National Foreign Language 2020

Project, English proficiency among university graduates has become a strategic educational goal. Consequently, Vietnamese universities have increasingly adopted international textbooks for English language instruction. However, this shift prompts critical reflection on how such textbooks influence the teaching and learning process in Vietnamese classrooms, where cultural, linguistic, and contextual needs may differ significantly from the environments for which these materials were originally developed. Although this article focuses specifically on Vietnam, these debates are taking place globally and the conclusions may contribute to this wider discourse.

The present article is based on a study that investigated how lecturers and students in a Vietnamese university perceive and use global English textbooks in their teaching and learning. It explores the extent to which these materials support or constrain effective pedagogical practices and student engagement. Through a mixed-methods case study design involving interviews and survey data, this study, unlike many other studies, combines teacher and student perspectives in the Vietnamese higher education context.

The study was guided by this research question:

To what extent, and in what ways, does textbook use impact teaching and learning in higher education in Vietnam?

The next section contextualises this study within current research literature. This is followed by a discussion of methods and the presentation and discussion of the findings.

2 Literature Review

Textbooks have long been central to formal education systems across the world. Over thirty years ago, Apple (1991) and Altbach (1991) noted that when textbooks written in one country are used in global contexts they do not simply transmit knowledge, they also encode ideologies, teaching philosophies, and cultural assumptions. Indeed, research has shown that English textbooks designed and published by ‘inner-circle’ (Kobayashi, 2018: 559) publishers tend to provide more information about the culture of origin than the local culture of delivery (Rahim & Daghigh, 2020; Alawlaqi & Dihliza, 2023), compared to textbooks published within any given country (Ayu, 2020). Since the 1990s, in the last three decades the market for English language textbooks has grown enormously and become increasingly globalised (Yildiz & Harwood, 2024). International publishers such as Pearson, Oxford University Press, and Cambridge University Press now dominate the ELT textbook market in many countries, including Vietnam (Dang & Seals, 2018).

Global textbooks, sometimes referred to as ‘imported textbooks’ or ‘international coursebooks’, are characterised by standardised content designed to appeal to a wide audience (Vo & Tran, 2025). This audience of lecturers and learners is expected to gain pedagogical advantages by using textbooks that are widely and internationally

adopted (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2007; Le, 2012). However, this widespread adoption raises an ongoing debate about their limitations in addressing the diverse needs of learners in specific educational contexts (Gray, 2010; Tomlinson, 2010; Tao, 2012; Marlina, 2025)

Several studies over several decades have documented the benefits of using global textbooks in language education. Cunningsworth (1995) and McGrath (2013) argued that high-quality textbooks can provide structured learning pathways, well-sequenced grammar and vocabulary input, and engaging language activities. Tomlinson (2011) emphasised that textbooks can serve as the *de facto* syllabus, offering pedagogical guidance, pacing, and content alignment with international frameworks such as the CEFR, which in some contexts provide important structure. Textbooks are also seen as valuable tools for reducing teacher workload (Richards, 2001). Teachers benefit from having ready-made materials that are visually appealing, professionally edited, and consistent across courses. For novice teachers, textbooks offer scaffolding, while for experienced educators, they provide a foundation upon which to build creative and adaptive practices (Carabantes & Paran, 2022). From the learners' perspective, textbooks offer familiarity, predictability, and a clear structure (Xiong & Qian, 2012). Parents and administrators often view textbook-based education as credible and legitimate (Yu, 2001; Le, 2012). In countries such as Vietnam, where English is a high-stakes subject, textbooks can help align classroom instruction with standardised assessments (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2007; Fang et al., 2022).

However, despite their popularity, global textbooks have been criticised for several reasons:

- Scholars have noted that many textbooks are culturally biased, often reflecting Western norms and perspectives that are misaligned with learners' sociocultural contexts (Dat, 2008; Ross & Forman, 2014). This mismatch can hinder student engagement and make classroom interactions less meaningful (Dahmardeh & Kim, 2021; Carabantes, 2022).
- Global textbooks often prioritise Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which may clash with local teaching traditions or institutional constraints. In Vietnam, for example, where exam-oriented learning and large class sizes are common, CLT-oriented tasks such as pair work, projects, or open discussions are difficult to implement effectively (Mai & Iwashita, 2012).
- Textbooks can inadvertently narrow lecturers' autonomy; when curricula are tightly bound to a particular textbook, instructors may feel compelled to "teach to the book", which limits the space for adaptation and responsiveness to learner needs (Gebhard, 2006: 105).

Numerous scholars (e.g., Harmer, 2011; González Hernández, 2022) argue that the teacher's role is critical in determining the success of textbook implementation. Teachers at best may act as mediators between textbook content and learner experience. Their professional judgment enables them to adapt, modify, or supplement textbook materials based on students' proficiency, interests, and learning styles. Teachers who possess the autonomy and confidence to critique and contextualise textbooks are more likely to use them as flexible tools rather than rigid scripts (Carabantes, 2022). However, this requires not only pedagogical expertise but also institutional support and training. Previous research has found that in practice,

especially in developing contexts, teachers may be under-resourced and overburdened, making textbook dependence a default choice (Vo & Tran, 2025).

Lastly, textbooks are often closely tied to assessment practices. Many global textbooks provide test banks, progress checks, and end-of-unit reviews that align with their instructional content. This can be advantageous, offering coherence between teaching and testing. However, relying solely on textbook-based assessments can constrain formative feedback and reduce the opportunity for more authentic, learner-centered evaluation practices (Shepard, 2000; Jiang 2013; Frey 2014).

3 Method

The case study presented here employed a mixed-methods approach to explore the impact of global textbooks on teaching and learning at a Vietnamese university. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with five English lecturers and a survey administered to 23 university students. The rationale for using mixed methods lies in the complementarity of qualitative and quantitative insights. While interviews provide depth and context to teachers' perspectives, surveys offer breadth and enable a cross comparison with students' responses. This approach enabled triangulation, thus enhancing the validity of our findings.

The interview participants were three General English lecturers and two Business English lecturers, all from the Faculty of English Language at a university in Vietnam. They had substantial teaching experience and used a range of international textbooks, including: Cutting Edge (Cunningham et al., 2013), Speak Now (Richards & Bohlke, 2012), English for Negotiating (LaFond et al., 2010):

No	Interviewee's Pseudonym	Gender	Years of Teaching Experience	Age	Title
1	Ha	Female	10	38	Senior Lecturer
2	Vi	Female	7	33	Lecturer
3	Loc	Male	12	38	Senior Lecturer
4	Lan	Female	12	40	Senior Lecturer
5	Tan	Male	11	34	Lecturer

Table 1: Interviewees

The students surveyed were enrolled in both English-major and non-English-major programmes. This university is typical of many Vietnamese institutions in that: textbooks are mandated by curriculum, assessment is centralized, and instruction is often exam-focused.

The lecturer interviews were conducted online and lasted approximately 20 to 30 minutes each. The interview questions covered topics such as the use of textbooks, strategies for adapting them, teaching philosophy and the perceived impact of lecturers on student learning. The student questionnaire comprised 21 items, incorporating multiple-choice, Likert scale and open-ended questions. Topics included the frequency of textbook use, perceived usefulness, skills development and suggestions for improvement. The interview data were transcribed and analyzed thematically. The survey responses were processed using descriptive statistics. Ethical procedures based on British Education Research Association guidelines (BERA, 2024), including informed consent and data anonymization, were followed throughout.

4 Findings

This section presents the detailed findings derived from the two data collection methods: semi-structured interviews with English lecturers and a quantitative survey administered to students at the participating University in Vietnam. The findings are presented separately for each participant group, followed by a synthesis of the key discoveries so as to offer a complete picture of the role of the textbook in this specific institutional context. The findings from the interviews are presented first.

4.1 Teachers' Perspectives

The semi-structured interviews with lecturers provided a nuanced understanding of their experiences and perceptions regarding the use of global textbooks. This is detailed below.

4.1.1 Benefits and Constraints

The data indicates that while textbooks were considered by these participants to be indispensable pedagogical tools, their effectiveness was seen as heavily contingent on the lecturer's ability to adapt the materials to the specific context of his or her classroom. However, the research also revealed that the lecturers at the institution where the research was conducted self-defined as skilled and creative in their approach to textbook usage. A very high level of agreement emerged in the interviews with all the interviewees positively and in some detail describing their autonomy as session designers and lecturers.

All five lecturers acknowledged the central role of textbooks in their teaching. They described how textbooks provide structure, standardise language input, and enable alignment with end-of-course assessments. For example, Vi stated that:

We have to follow the content because 60% of the test is based on the textbook.¹

¹ In the interviewee's quotes, the original wordings, including aspects of potentially natural conversational style have been kept verbatim to preserve the authenticity of the data.

Alongside this institutional pressure, there was a sense of appreciation for the pedagogical support provided by the materials. The lecturers consistently emphasised that modern textbooks promote creativity, project work, and student collaboration. Ha said:

Students are more engaged because the content feels relevant and the visuals are interesting.

Nevertheless, a need for creativity and autonomy emerged. The lecturers were again consistent in that all critiqued certain activities as either too challenging or too culturally distant from students' lived experiences. Four out of five lecturers reported having to replace entire sections or supplement them with online videos or handouts and all described developing additional materials. Although one lecturer (Vi the least experienced) acknowledged doing this to a slightly lesser extent, limiting this largely to additional tasks based on textbook materials. Lan explained:

Some textbooks are too difficult for lower-level students; others are too easy. We have to constantly adjust.

Ha described a case where a textbook designed for intermediate-level students used too broad a range of language registers, concepts and context specific vocabulary in its listening sections, which hindered the students' ability to complete the tasks and impacted on their confidence as language users. This required the lecturer to "*find alternative material*" (Lan) that was more appropriate for the students' abilities and needs..

Similarly, Loc found the reading content in textbooks to be overly difficult or culturally irrelevant.

...sometimes the level of the text is not suitable for students. They don't have enough general knowledge to understand the text.

The lecturers also faced the challenge of mixed-ability classrooms, where some might find the textbooks to be too easy while others found them too difficult. Lan wryly stated that over-reliance on a single textbook could also "reduce even my interest first and then confidence later", suggesting a potential risk of pedagogical monotony.

4.1.2 The Teacher's Role in Adapting Textbooks

However, to counter these limitations, the lecturers who participated in this study described themselves as having a high degree of autonomy and skill in adapting and supplementing the textbook materials. Instead of following the textbook fully and rigidly, all viewed it as a "*starting point*" (Tan) and supplemented it with other resources to make lessons "*more lively and interesting.*" (Ha). As Tan stated:

I do it very often, especially in speaking lessons. I follow the communicative approach for speaking lessons so I like, for one lesson, I often go from mechanical drills so that the students will get used to the language, I mean the vocabulary and the structure for example. Then I move on to some free practice and I often include some like social activities in speaking lessons so that the students can use the English in a very natural way like they would do in the real context.

Another lecturer, Loc, said:

I don't use everything in the textbooks. I always have to redesign the activities that we have. I also use the linguistic input but I have to redesign the activities I mean the listening exercises

Ha said:

so I may use about 50 to 60% of the listening test in the book and then I will use some authentic materials outside the book.

It is noticeable that all the lecturers used supplementary materials such as "presentation slides with different images, or different questions or exercises" (*Lan*)

One interviewee was more cautious than others, but still exercised creativity. Vi described her approach as follows:

I must say that the textbook content is a must and we have to follow. If you don't follow it you know the result of this student will affect lecturers' assessment. So I need to combine, so I add more activities like using some pictures or some quiz to make them feel interested in my lesson more and then it's easier for me to teach the content, the textbook.

Another example provided was in speaking classes, in which Ha creatively supplemented materials to "bridge the gap between the textbook and the learning objectives."

These findings highlight that while textbooks are important, in this institution, the lecturer's intervention is a critical factor in ensuring effective instruction. These lecturers in this institution showed a high degree of confidence and autonomy, demonstrating this in the way that they used and supplemented the textbooks.

4.2 Student Survey Results

The survey was responded to by 23 Vietnamese students. They were all aged from 19 to 20 and studying on undergraduate degree courses at the same university in Vietnam. They were not asked to give their gender, as there was no intention to use this in the process of analysis. The first graph below illustrates textbook usage among the 23 students surveyed, with the second graph illustrating perceived effectiveness (Figure 1).

As the graphs above illustrate, textbooks remain a common learning resource among these participants, with 17 (74%) of the participating students using them regularly. For these students, textbooks play a notable role in assessment preparation: 15 (65%) relied on them for exam preparation and 12 (52%) used them for self-study. These students also viewed them as effective for receptive and form-focused learning, with a perception that they provide strong support for learning vocabulary (78%) and learning grammar (74%).

Figure 1: Textbook Usage Among Students

Figure 2: Perceived Effectiveness of Textbooks

In contrast, however, fewer students valued textbooks for productive skills: 13 (57%) disagreed that they improve speaking, and 10 (43%) were neutral or disagreed about textbooks benefiting their listening skills. Significantly, only 6 students (35%) considered textbooks to be their main study material, indicating that while textbooks are present in study routines, they are often supplemented by other resources. Furthermore, 7 students (30%) reported that textbook content could be confusing without the teacher’s explanations. In addition, 9 students (39%) noted that textbook tasks were often predictable and lacked authenticity. Overall, these findings suggest that students value textbooks for knowledge input but perceived weaknesses with textbooks in fostering communicative competence.

The most significant challenges students described themselves as facing were related to the content of the textbook itself. In response to open-ended questions on the questionnaire one student shared:

There are so many new words, so I need time to check the dictionary, which is time-consuming.

Another student noted:

I often find it very difficult to concentrate on the book.

Six students, in response to the open questions on the survey, thanked their teachers and stated that they particularly appreciated how lecturers in their higher education institution supplemented textbooks with real-life examples and integrated digital resources, even though this was not directly asked.

4.3 Student and Teacher Perceptions Compared

The findings from the lecturer interviews and student survey together reveal a nuanced picture of the textbook's role. Both groups recognised textbooks as useful tools that provide structure, learning materials, and support for assessment, particularly in vocabulary and grammar learning and exam preparation, but their effectiveness was not seen as absolute. Participants identified limitations related to cultural relevance, level appropriateness, and unengaging or predictable content, with some students finding tasks confusing without the lecturer's guidance. Only a minority of students relied on the textbook as their main study resource, while all lecturers creatively adapted and supplemented materials based on their professional experience and judgement. Acting as critical mediators, lecturers proactively incorporated real-life examples and digital resources to meet their students' specific needs, highlighting a pattern of agency and responsiveness that both lecturers and students valued in enhancing their learning.

5 Discussion

The findings of this study revealed a complex relationship between textbook content, teaching strategies, and learning outcomes, within the participating institution. Global textbooks, while widely adopted and institutionally mandated, are not neutral tools; they are pedagogical frameworks embedded within cultural, linguistic, and methodological assumptions (Vo & Tran, 2025). The lecturers and students who participated in this study showed an explicit understanding of this, which aligns with Tomlinson's (2010) assertion that while textbooks provide valuable input, their effectiveness depends on how they are used. The mismatch, that the lecturers described, between textbook design and classroom realities, particularly in terms of student proficiency and cultural relevance, is consistent with previous studies (Ross & Forman, 2014; Dahmardeh & Kim, 2021). Lecturers' adaptations were therefore consistently seen by the participants as not merely optional but necessary for pedagogical effectiveness. Significantly, this study found that the lecturers were creative and agentic in developing complementary materials. Previous studies have found this not to be the case in other similar contexts (Dat, 2008; Dang & Seals, 2018; Fang et al., 2022), or at least not as strongly the case (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2007; Le, 2012). The findings in this study therefore speak positively about lecturer confidence and self-efficacy in Vietnam.

Student responses underscored a dichotomy that has been found in previous research that textbooks are useful for receptive skills and test preparation but by themselves are inadequate for fostering communicative competence. This supports Jiang's (2013) critique of assessment-driven learning environments and suggests that textbooks alone cannot meet all language learning objectives. Institutionally, textbooks play a dual role: they standardise the curriculum and facilitate assessment, but they can also constrain innovation. Thus, a balance is needed where textbooks serve as scaffolds rather than straitjackets. The teachers and students in this study clearly understood this.

6 Conclusion

This study contributes to the growing literature on textbook use in ELT by offering an in-depth examination of how global textbooks function in a Vietnamese higher education context. Through teacher interviews and student surveys, it sheds light on the benefits, limitations, and adaptations surrounding textbook-driven instruction. Key findings indicate that while textbooks provide structure and assessment alignment, their pedagogical value depends on how they are contextualised by teachers. Cultural mismatch, skill-level misalignment, and limited speaking support emerged as core challenges. These findings largely reaffirm an already existing consensus. However, importantly, this study found a high degree of autonomy and creativity among the participating lecturers. These lecturers demonstrated resourcefulness in adapting content and confidence in doing so. This has not typically been found before by previous studies focused on institutions in developing economies. It should, of course, be noted that this study involved just one institution in Vietnam. Nevertheless, the lecturers in this study consistently supplemented global textbooks with real-life examples, digital resources, and culturally relevant adjustments. This suggests a possibly distinctive pattern of lecturer agency and pedagogical responsiveness in Vietnam's higher education context

Based on this, the authors' make the following recommendations:

1. For lecturers, professional development should focus on critical textbook use and adaptive teaching strategies.
2. For publishers, greater localisation and culturally responsive content are essential.
3. For policymakers, textbook adoption should be accompanied by teacher training and curriculum alignment strategies.
4. For institutions: flexibility in textbook implementation can enhance teaching quality; lecturers who demonstrate this should be supported and affirmed.

Future research could explore textbook adaptation practices in other regional contexts or examine the long-term effects of textbook use on student learning outcomes. As the global educational setting evolves, understanding how materials mediate learning in local contexts will remain a crucial area of inquiry.

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